

Jon D. Unruh

Reconstruction-induced land and property restitution in post-war Syria: The problem with sanctions

I. Introduction

With the war in Syria appearing to draw to a close – although not along the lines preferred by the West – the realities of what reconstruction will look like and how it will affect the post-war order have become primary considerations. As the nearly 13 million forcibly dislocated persons – along with the countries and communities that host them – contemplate possible returns to housing, land and property (HLP) within Syria, post-war reconstruction, return migration and restitution emerge as strongly linked. Dislocated populations will not consider returning to areas of origin in significant numbers without reconstruction and the recovery of livelihood opportunities that reconstruction provides.¹

As long as large parts of the country continue to be uninhabitable, the dislocation crises in neighbouring countries, Europe and across Syria will continue.² While it is in the West's interest to encourage returns to areas of origin and restitution of HLP in the interests of fair, just and secure recovery of livelihoods and overall stability, Western sanctions on reconstruction actively thwart such a process, particularly in government-held areas, which constitute most of the country. For the European and Middle Eastern countries most affected by the presence of large numbers of refugees, this is a fundamentally fraught but important deliberation. Migration and refugee return will be at the centre of these discussions. Faced with a lack

of reconstruction and the resulting deficit of livelihood and economic opportunities, refugees will not willingly return; and with the surrounding states resisting their integration, many more may decide to move on to Europe.³ And while fewer returns would mean less pressure on the Syrian government to attend to the needs of the overall population, including for HLP restitution,⁴ the reverse is also true – effective reconstruction, safely drawing back significant numbers of refugees and internally dislocated persons (IDPs) would pressure the government to meet the restitution and livelihood recovery needs of its post-war population. Without such pressure, expropriation interests are more likely to emerge.⁵

This article examines the intersection between reconstruction and HLP restitution, with a focus on rural areas, and argues that Western sanctions are in need of realignment.

II. The sanctions narrative

At present the West finds itself in a bind with regard to the relationship between reconstruction and refugee and IDP returns. As the war progressed, Western donor countries were waiting for the Syrian government to fall before providing reconstruction funds. With this scenario not having played out, the West has imposed a wide array of sanctions on Syria that prohibit reconstruction, with the thinking being that such prohibitions are useful as leverage to encourage a political

¹ El-Gamal, *The displacement dilemma: should Europe help Syrian refugees return home?*, 2019.

² Calamur, *No one wants to help Bashar al-Assad rebuild Syria*, 2019.

³ Decina, *How should the West play a weak hand in Syria reconstruction?*, 2019.

⁴ El-Gamal, *The displacement dilemma: should Europe help Syrian refugees return home?*, 2019.

⁵ Itani, *Geo-economics: Russia and Iran in Syria*, 2019.

transition in the country.⁶ In spite of the faint prospects for such a transition, there is a strong desire among Western governments to not back down and to maintain sanctions.⁷ Meanwhile, “[t]here are growing concerns that political strategies and slogans are overshadowing necessary, technical discussions on transitioning from solely emergency responses to dignified, sustainable, cost-effective support for fragile communities.”⁸

The existence and operational format of the West’s sanctions against reconstruction in Syria emerge from a narrative that is shaped by discussions in Western capitals focusing almost exclusively on one aspect of the Syrian dilemma – the al-Assad administration and its human rights atrocities, form of governance and alliances with Russia and Iran. However, an important distinction regarding the sanctions is the domain in which they are intended to operate versus the domain they actually impact. The sanctions are intended to operate at the political level, to achieve a political outcome and coerce the government into a political transition or political concessions. As a result, the focus from outside the country on state control, the activities of the Syrian government, the role of foreign players and human rights violations depends on sanctions being a vehicle whose purpose and goal is a change in this domain.⁹ While unlikely at this point, such a focus has a profoundly negative effect on the needs and processes of reconstruction, returns, restitution, livelihood

recovery and actual on-the-ground stabilisation. As Said and Yazigi¹⁰ note, “a bad sanctions policy could feed political polarization in favour of Assad.” Omar¹¹ likewise observes that “[s]anctions empower the well-connected while others suffer.”

III. Not a conventional post-war recovery

While prevailing approaches to post-war recovery commonly support working towards building the credibility of a recovering government so as to facilitate population returns and reconstruction, Western governments have actively sought the opposite in Syria in an attempt to align the post-war order with Western expectations.¹² In cases such as Syria, the application of sanctions assumes that there will be a weakening of control by reticent governments as they move towards fragility or failure and thus acquiescence. But Syria has not complied with this logic. Instead it has arguably become a ‘fierce state’ as opposed to a fragile or failed state.¹³ As a result, it has now become clear that there will not be a conventional, internationally assisted and supervised refugee/IDP return and restitution process that applies accepted forms of transitional justice, transparency, rule of law, human rights and effective remedies, as is the norm after most wars. This is a significant problem given the daunting prospects for HLP in the post-war phase. The possibility of large-scale demographic change, widespread confiscations,¹⁴ damage and destruction,¹⁵

⁶ Dahi, *Syria: donor conditionality, sanctions, and the question of justice*, 2019; Celso, *Superpower hybrid warfare in Syria*, 2018; Decina, *How should the West play a weak hand in Syria reconstruction?*, 2019; Calamur, *No one wants to help Bashar al-Assad rebuild Syria*, 2019; Cafarella, *Time to recommit to Syria*, 2020.

⁷ Said and Yazigi, *The reconstruction of Syria: Socially just re-integration and peace building or regime re-consolidation*, 2018; Imady, *The weaponization of Syria’s reconstruction: A preliminary sketch*, 2019.

⁸ Achilles and Hemsley, *Aid in limbo: Why Syrians deserve support to rebuild their lives*, 2019.

⁹ Cafarella, *Time to recommit to Syria*, 2020; Imady, *The weaponization of Syria’s reconstruction: A preliminary sketch*, 2019.

¹⁰ Said and Yazigi, *The reconstruction of Syria: Socially just re-integration and peace building or regime re-consolidation*, 2018.

¹¹ Dahi, *Syria: donor conditionality, sanctions, and the question of justice*, 2019.

¹² Decina, *How should the West play a weak hand in Syria reconstruction?*, 2019; Dahi, *Syria: donor conditionality, sanctions, and the question of justice*, 2019; Cafarella, *Time to recommit to Syria*, 2020.

¹³ Almanasfi, *State-led Iran development in Syria and the prospects for effective post-conflict reconstruction*, 2018.

¹⁴ Vignal, *Locating dispossession and HLP rights in the war in Syria*, 2019.

¹⁵ Imady, *The weaponization of Syria’s reconstruction: A preliminary sketch*, 2019.

application of abusive expropriation laws¹⁶ and political agendas¹⁷ will be primary concerns. And while there are many predictions regarding the highly negative HLP scenarios and resulting instability these could produce, research from inside the country indicates that these issues will interact with an array of countervailing forces able to induce HLP restitution, acting through specific forms of reconstruction. What are these forms of reconstruction-induced restitution operable in Syria and what is their potential?

IV. Reconstruction-induced restitution: The role of civil society organisations

While the forms of reconstruction-induced restitution vary, they all depend on ways in which specific reconstruction activities are able to (re)attach people to place. This occurs through variations on a central scenario in which reconstruction encourages returns and reengagement in the spatial aspects of livelihoods, which then act to reinvigorate local civil society organisations (CSOs) that were used prior to the war, which play an important role in socio-legal attachment to place. This role occurs because the membership of CSOs know where everyone resided prior to the war, thereby facilitating and legitimising returns to original HLP. Such widely held knowledge then also acts as a deterrent to secondary occupations and expropriations.

Local livelihood CSOs are surprisingly abundant in rural Syria, ranging from irrigation water user associations to peasant associations, local branches of the General Union of Peasants, chambers of agriculture, agricultural commodity processing groups and the pervasive local (neighbourhood) committees. Local committees comprise the local Muktar and local government officials as well as civil society members. Such committees, particularly in their relationships with local govern-

ment and other CSOs, are able to manage a variety of post-war HLP rights problems: secondary occupations, counter-claims, returns, a returning female head of household whose husband is absent, etc. Local committees were quite active during the war in this regard, and humanitarian organisations used them extensively to select beneficiaries for aid programmes, particularly in programmes which sought to target the most vulnerable. And while local committees have been highlighted as having been a vehicle for government penetration of civil society prior to the war, in a post-war scenario this same relationship can favour HLP restitution by obligating local government to acknowledge restitution claims.

Prior to the war, the relationships between CSOs and government provided important linkages between government legitimacy at different levels and HLP facts on the ground; including the history of government interaction with the various CSOs and their members. In many cases CSOs had linkages with the Ba'ath party, to mutual benefit. Thus, large-scale attempts to dislocate (or refuse return to) communities by a particular branch of government would come up against this important set of relationships with other branches, encountering a significant number of people, institutions and organisations that would be aware of the attempted expropriation. This would likely work against successfully appropriating land by: 1) forestalling an area being selected for such action, 2) enhancing the prospect that such an action would be rescinded eventually, and 3) amplifying the number of people (and the positions they occupy) that could act to thwart expropriations, particularly in such a patronage-prone place as Syria. Attempts at large-scale expropriations in this context would essentially violate the local government's role to the degree that forms of local

¹⁶ J., *Law No. 10: Property rights violations in Syria against sustainable solutions for returnees*, 2019.

¹⁷ Fabbe and Sinmazdemir, *Syrian refugees in Turkey and the politics of reconciliation*, 2018; McGee, *Nothing is ours anymore - HLP rights violations in Syria*, 2019.

government may cease to function, as certainly the numerous CSOs would – with significant implications for stability.

Thus, while there will certainly be some confiscation of HLP for certain projects and in order to attempt greater control in certain opposition locations,¹⁸ this may be difficult to accomplish in a large-scale way. Given the historical integration of CSOs with government networks, large-scale expropriations could set local government against central government and thus act as a further deterrent, particularly given the new ‘decentralisation role’ that a recent law has provided to local government, which increases their agency.¹⁹ At the same time, however, significant delays in reconstruction – resulting in much reduced refugee/IDP returns – do provide more opportunity for such expropriations, as perhaps evidenced by the recent reported provision of significant farming acreage to Iranian interests.²⁰ This illustrates a dilemma in that the lack of reconstruction can contribute to expropriations, which then constitute a reason for continuing to withhold reconstruction funding.

V. Examples of reconstruction-induced restitution

The reconstruction of irrigation infrastructure stands out as a particularly important form of reconstruction-induced restitution in rural areas, primarily due to the strong connection between water rights, water user CSOs and land rights. Prior to the war, CSO members had irrigation water rights, and thus also had to have land rights in order to use the water, such that re-establishing irrigation water delivery drives the reconnection of land rights to water rights to claimants. This is important given that irrigation networks in Syria serve quite large numbers of people, and the

government’s current strategy for irrigation rehabilitation is to reconstruct the large public networks first because these serve the most people. The overall effect of this approach would be to drive reattachment to irrigated land over wide areas for large numbers of people.

Water user CSOs are very old in Syria and have previously endured and recovered from war. Some areas of Syria have been under irrigation for over 2,000 years,²¹ and so the cooperative aspect and interconnectedness of landholders in irrigated areas are quite high. The ability of water-user CSOs to ‘know where everyone belongs’ and re-establish tenure rights to individuals and families connected to land served by specific irrigation canals is quite robust. There is also very close coordination and cooperation between these water user CSOs and local government (often the Ministry of Water) – with government representatives participating in the activities of the CSOs and CSO members participating in regional and local government decisions and meetings that affect them. Such cooperation is the kind of interaction the UN and other international donors encouraged in Syria prior to the war as a form of good governance.

The distribution of seeds is another important example of reconstruction and restitution. Because seed distribution is also regarded as humanitarian assistance, it has been able to avoid the application of sanctions and so provides important insights into the use of various forms of reconstruction activities in restitution. Seed distribution in Syria is a widespread activity involving hundreds of thousands of beneficiaries in different parts of the country. The primary intersection between seed distribution and restitution is that use of seeds in planting reinforces the attachment of

¹⁸ The Syria Report, *Northern Hama’s pistachio farmers restricted from their lands during late harvest*, 2020.

¹⁹ Araabi, *Syria’s decentralization roadmap*, 2017.

²⁰ Itani, *Geo-economics: Russia and Iran in Syria*, 2019.

²¹ Caponera, *Water laws in Moslem countries*, 1954.

people to land to which they claim some form of rights. This occurs through 1) the facts-on-the-ground act of planting, 2) the broader community acknowledgement of rights that permits use of seeds on certain land by specific people, and importantly, 3) receiving the seeds in the first place as a beneficiary.

Agricultural assistance provided by the international community, such as the provision of seeds, fertiliser and pesticides, is not randomly distributed in Syria, nor is it distributed by request only. Instead they are provided through very carefully derived beneficiary lists put together by the local leadership along with recognised and long-standing farmer CSOs and affiliated members of local government (all of whom know which people belong on which farmland). The derivation of such lists is monitored and supported by donors or NGOs, who then provide the assistance. Such beneficiaries can be attached to land through any number of ways of tenure – ownership, rent, borrowing, inheritance, sharecropping, ‘permitted squatters’ and caretakers – along with claims by returning refugee IDPs as well as female heads of household and children with missing partners or parents. Thus, those without recognised long-term presence on the land are not included in beneficiary lists and do not receive inputs, nor would they be permitted to use them by the local community, donors or local government as a way to claim land.

Beneficiary use of agricultural seeds and other inputs provided by donors can have further restitution utility through the criteria that donors and NGOs place on assistance. For example, the Aga Khan Foundation focuses on providing agricultural inputs to the most vulnerable small-scale farmers. The foundation chooses not to rely on government registers of landowners to form its beneficiary lists, as this would exclude renters, female heads of household and children with missing parents along with those that have inherited

land without updating the registry. Renters alone comprise 20% of the farmers in the area that Aga Khan operates in.

The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) is another example of a seed distribution donor. For its beneficiary lists, it establishes a local committee comprised of existing community representatives along with members of local government (Ministry of Agriculture). Land ownership is verified by the Muktar, local leaders and a government registry for the area – although the latter can be lacking in up-to-date information. In many cases the male head of household is not present and the beneficiary is a woman, who while not on a government list of landowners is nonetheless known to local committee members as being attached to local land, and so is placed on the beneficiary list and provided with inputs for the land in question. While criteria for deriving beneficiary lists can vary among donors, the objective for most is to target as many small-scale farmers as possible as opposed to the relatively few larger-scale farmers, with the effect of strengthening small-holder claims and tenure security. For some seed distribution activities, the majority of beneficiaries may be women due to targeting criteria that selects the most food insecure households. And because beneficiary lists are drawn up based on pre-war land attachments, the effect is to support returns to the same locations and tenure arrangements as existed prior to the conflict, as opposed to land ownership and access being restructured by the incidental or purposeful repercussions of the conflict.

Other forms of rural reconstruction also support restitution. The rehabilitation of livestock herds is one of these, with veterinary assistance (and the attendant beneficiary lists) inducing reaccess to grazing land as herd sizes grow, and hence the reassertion of claims to this land. In the case of Aga Khan, the focus for livestock herd reconstruction is

on the more arid areas, where the poorer herders are and where access to grazing land is most important. Reestablishing plantations of economic trees along with rehabilitation of land via landmine clearing also reattaches people to land, involving claims by previous owners and occupants. Some Syrian refugees even explicitly use reconstruction to support reacquisition of their land. One such approach (also relevant to urban areas) involves refugees negotiating the reconstruction of the land they are returning to in exchange for part of the land or property being provided to the reconstruction company. Such an agreement positions both the landowner and the company carrying out the reconstruction activity (often politically connected) against any attempt at expropriation.

VI. Conclusion

Having a reformed Syria be the end goal of the West's sanctions at this point in the war appears misplaced given the nature of the conflict. The war is now much, much larger and more amplified, complex and problematic than a reformed government and its relationship with civil society could resolve. The humanitarian calamity, the millions of displaced, the horrific way the war has been conducted, the presence of extremist groups, the tangle of alliances and multiple proxy wars as well as the political repercussions of millions of refugees scattered throughout parts of the Middle East and Europe are now far worse

than the original cause of the conflict and well beyond what a reformed Syrian government could solve. While punishing the regime for its vast human rights abuses is certainly warranted, the way current sanctions are structured punishes the wrong people. HLP restitution attached to specific forms of reconstruction could play a very important role in the emerging post-war order. Restitution induced by the provision of inputs, derivation of beneficiary lists, reconstruction of agricultural infrastructure, enhanced capacity of CSOs, rehabilitation of livestock herds, mine clearance and reestablishing plantations of economic trees, along with other forms of reconstruction in government areas, can directly oppose expropriation processes. While this article looked at restitution in rural areas as an example, an important question is what forms of reconstruction-induced restitution could operate in urban areas?

As the war in Syria draws to a close, the stabilisation and recovery of large parts of the country will depend to a significant degree on restituting HLP rights for those who fled. Given the absence of a conventional large-scale, internationally mediated restitution process – and the presence of expropriating legislation, interests and agendas – reconstruction-induced forms of restitution warrant greater attention in the application of policy and practice for Syria and other war-affected countries where Western donors and the UN have limited reach.

Reference list

ACHILLES, KATHRYN AND MATHEW HEMSLEY, "Aid in limbo. Why Syrians deserve support to rebuild their lives," *Oxfam International and The Danish Refugee Council*, March 2019, <https://tinyurl.com/y5sule86>.

ALMANASFI, NADINE, "State-led Iran development in Syria and the prospects for effective post-conflict reconstruction," *Syria Studies* 11 (1:2019), 58-99.

ARAABI, SAMER, "Syria's decentralization roadmap," *Carnegie Endowment for International Peace*, March 23, 2017, <https://carnegieendowment.org/sada/68372>.

CAFARELLA, JENNIFER, "Time to recommit to Syria," *Foreign Affairs*, February 18, 2020, <https://tinyurl.com/y3zz9yla>.

CALAMUR, KRISHNADEV, "No one wants to help Bashar al-Assad rebuild Syria," *The Atlantic*, March 15, 2019, <https://tinyurl.com/y2jxtluc>.

CAPONERA, DANTE A., "Water laws in Moslem countries," *FAO Development Paper*, Number 43, 1954.

CELSE, ANTHONY N., "Superpower hybrid warfare in Syria," *Marine Corps University Journal* 9 (2:2018), 92-116.

DAHI, OMAR, "Syria: donor conditionality, sanctions, and the question of justice," *London School of Economics and Political Science*, March 6, 2019, <https://tinyurl.com/y6dauabx>.

DECINA, ALEXANDER, "How should the West play a weak hand in Syria reconstruction?," *War on the Rocks*, February 1, 2019, <https://tinyurl.com/ycwj5sfz>.

EL-GAMAL, JASMINE M., "The displacement dilemma: should Europe help Syrian refugees return home?," Policy Brief, *European Council on Foreign Relations*, March 2019, <https://tinyurl.com/y4r8rfn8>.

FABBE, KRISTIN AND TOLGA SINMAZDEMIR, "Syrian refugees in Turkey and the politics of reconciliation," *Review of Middle East Studies* 52 (2:2018), 249-262.

IMADY, OMAR, "The weaponization of Syria's reconstruction. A preliminary sketch," *Syria Studies* 11 (1:2019), 6-21.

ITANI, FAYSAL, "Geo-economics. Russia and Iran in Syria," *Syria Studies* 11 (1:2019), 3-31.

J., ISABEL, "Law No. 10: Property rights violations in Syria against sustainable solutions for returnees," *Shattuck Center*, Central European University, 2019, <https://tinyurl.com/y3xt6slp>.

MCGEE, THOMAS, "Nothing is ours anymore - HLP rights violations in Syria," in *Reclaiming home: The struggle for socially just housing, land and property rights in Syria, Iraq, and Libya*, edited by Baumann, Hannes (Berlin: Friedrich-Ebert-Stiftung, 2019), 120-140, <https://tinyurl.com/yy6ylr9f>.

SAID, SALAM AND JIHAD YAZIGI, "The reconstruction of Syria. Socially just re-integration and peace building or regime re-consolidation," *Friedrich-Ebert-Stiftung*, December 2018, <https://tinyurl.com/y62jhmdy>.

THE SYRIA REPORT, "Northern Hama's pistachio farmers restricted from their lands during late harvest," August 26, 2020, <https://tinyurl.com/yxzvkrsk>.

VIGNAL, LEÏLA, "Locating dispossession and HLP rights in the war in Syria," in *Reclaiming home: The struggle for socially just housing, land and property rights in Syria, Iraq, and Libya*, edited by Baumann, Hannes (Berlin: Friedrich-Ebert-Stiftung, 2019), 18-31, <https://tinyurl.com/yy6ylr9f>.

All internet sources were accessed and verified on August 31, 2020.